

Deep learning-based post-contrast imaging free of exogenous contrast agents

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Gadolinium based contrast agents (GBCAs) have become a cornerstone in clinical routine for the detection of blood brain barrier (BBB) damage, a keynote in high-grade gliomas [1]. However, adverse reactions and the possible deposition of the GBCAs in the brain, especially in patients who need to undergo several follow-up acquisitions, have recently raised safety concerns [2,3]. We propose a cascade of deep networks for pre- and post-contrast parametric mapping and the synthesis of post-contrast T1-weighted (post-T1w) images from only two pre-contrast images (a T1w and a T2w) acquired with routine sequences.

METHODS: 14 patients with different grades of gliomas were acquired with IRB approval and informed written consent using a 3T GE Sigma Premier system. All patients had undergone tumor resection before the scan. For each patient, the imaging protocol consisted of four weighted images — T1w, T2w, T2w-FLAIR and post-T1w — together with MAGiC, a fast technique for multi-parametric mapping. All the image modalities were co-registered and skull-stripped.

We propose a cascade of two CNNs, namely, a normalization network and a prediction network. The first CNN extracts the quantitative T1, T2, and PD information embedded in the T1w and T2w images. Parametric maps are known to be more robust against scanner imperfections than weighted images. The second CNN takes previous T1 and T2 maps as input and predicts GBCA-related information using both the tissue information obtained by the parametric maps and the extra knowledge offered by the post-T1w and T2w during training; specifically, the output of the prediction network is the post-contrast T1 and T2 maps. The post-T1w is synthesized from post-contrast parametric maps using the theoretical equations that describe MR image intensity.

Both CNNs share the same architecture [4]. The training approach is 2-fold; 1) the training of the normalization network is supervised, with T1w as input and the output consists of the maps provided by MAGiC. 2) The prediction network is trained with a self-supervised learning similar to that proposed in Ref.[4], and with post-T1w and T2w as references. During the training of the prediction network the weights of the normalization network are fixed. The training was performed following a leave-one-out scheme. For each data splitting, one patient is used for testing and the remaining patients are randomly split between training (11 patients) and early-stopping validation (2 patients). Both networks share the same patient splitting.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: Figure 1 shows the pre- and post-contrast T1 and T2 maps, PD maps, and both the synthesized and acquired post-T1w images. The proposed method enables quantitative parametric mapping from two pre-contrast routine weighted images. In addition, preliminary results reveal the potential of this approach for obtaining equivalent information without GBCAs. Nevertheless, further investigation is needed.

Figure 1: A representative axial slice of the pre-contrast and post-contrast computed parametric maps (T1, T2, and PD) and the acquired and synthesized post-contrast T1w (post-T1w) images on two test patients. Arrows indicate the enhancement visible in post-T1w, which correspond with a reduction of the values in the quantitative post-contrast T1 map.

References

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